

IRRIGATION WATER SALINITY LIMITS FABA BEAN (*VICIA FABA* L.) PHOTOSYNTHESIS*

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SUMMARY: *Determination of plant salt stress responses is essential for stabilization of crop productivity under saline conditions. It is known that high soil salinity may adversely affect photosynthesis, which is a prerequisite for biomass production. For this reason, there is a considerable interest in measuring the photosynthetic rate of horticultural crops under saline conditions. A greenhouse pot experiment was set up to study the effects of saline irrigation water on faba bean (*Vicia faba* L.) photosynthetic rate and chlorophyll content index. Faba bean seedlings were transplanted into pots and treated with saline irrigation water. NaCl salinity was applied in a nutrient solution as follows: NaCl₀ – control (basic nutrient solution without added NaCl), NaCl₅₀ (control + 50 mM NaCl) and NaCl₁₀₀ (control + 100 mM NaCl). Five weeks after salinity treatment started faba bean leaf intercellular CO₂ concentration (C_i), stomatal conductance (g_s), transpiration rate (E), photosynthetic rate (A) and chlorophyll content index (CCI) were measured. Stomatal conductance, transpiration rate and photosynthetic rate of faba bean plants irrigated with saline water significantly decreased (P<0.01) in regard to control plants, but without significant difference amongst treatments. Intercellular CO₂ concentration was not significantly affected by application of saline irrigation water. Salinity treatments significantly altered (P=0.01) chlorophyll content index, although the influence was not linear to the salinity treatments. Raised soil salinity imposed water limitation for faba bean plants, which was suggested by lower stomatal conductance. Plant adaptive responses to salt stress include retention of water by stomatal closure, decreasing both transpiration and photosynthetic rate. Therefore application of saline irrigation water results in decreased rate of transpiration and limits faba bean photosynthesis as well.*

Key words: *NaCl, stress, transpiration, photosynthetic rate, chlorophyll*

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INTRODUCTION

Raising world food demands impose high productivity as the aim of the agricultural production, an objective inconceivable without extensive crop irrigation. However, extensive irrigation of crops favors secondary salinization of soil, deleteriously affecting soil properties and limiting the productivity of crops (Romic et al., 2008). Salinity affects 20% and up to 50% of the irrigated land worldwide (Pitman and Laüchli, 2002) and that percentage is expected to increase even more in the future (Tejera et al., 2006). Accumulation of soluble salts in the rhizosphere induces plant salt stress. Salt stress, amongst other physiological and morphological disorders which may emerge, disrupts plant pigment composition and decreases photosynthesis (Radwan et al., 2000), ultimately reflecting on crop productivity (Wang et al., 2003). It is essential to determine how plants respond to high soil salinity in order to improve crop productivity under saline conditions. Photosynthesis, as a prerequisite for biomass production, is considered a valuable parameter when studying plant adaptive responses to salinity (Radwan et al., 2000). In this context, measuring the photosynthetic rate of horticultural crops under saline conditions is useful tool in managing salinity stress.

Salinity affects photosynthesis via reduction in leaf area, chlorophyll content and stomatal conductance, but also through a decrease in photosystem II efficiency (Chinnusamy et al., 2006). Generally, restriction of photosynthesis by excessive salts in the rhizosphere may be divided to non-stomatal and stomatal limitations (Debez et al., 2006). Salt stress restrains product export in primary reactions of photosynthesis, which ultimately results in electron transport inhibition, increased chlorophyll fluorescence light emission, as well as enhanced reactive oxygen species (ROS) production (Koyro et al., 2010). Secondary effect of salt stress, mostly induced by abscisic acid (ABA) released from the plant roots, is stomatal closure and consequent inhibition of gas exchange (Koyro et al., 2010).

Faba bean (*Vicia faba* L.) is a legume crop produced worldwide because of its high yield and protein content (Daur et al., 2010). Based on the water stress day index, Katejri et al. (2000) specified faba bean as moderately sensitive to salinity, becoming less sensitive at later stages of development (Al-Tahir and Al-Abdulsalam 1997). Salinity effects on faba bean photosynthesis and chlorophyll content has been studied as well, yet the obtained results do not seem to show a consistent trend or a pattern. For example, El Sayed (2011) reported NaCl treatments did not generate a coherent trend in faba bean photosynthetic activity. Garg and Singla (2004) found that the response of photosynthesis of chickpea cultivars under salt stress was not as pronounced as the response of nitrogen fixation. Furthermore, Abdul Qados (2011) found differences in total chlorophyll content measured 10 days after NaCl salinity treatments started (decreased) and measured at the death of 40% of plants (increased in regard to control plants). For this reason, faba bean photosynthetic rate and total chlorophyll content under saline conditions was measured in order to elucidate plant responses to salt stress.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study was carried out from April, 2 – June, 15, in a greenhouse at the experimental station of the Faculty of Agriculture University of Zagreb, Croatia. Faba bean seedlings were grown from seeds in a polystyrene cups containing a peat soil (Potgrond P, Klasmann), and after three weeks uniform plants were transplanted into pots (one plant per pot) filled with agricultural soil. Pots were irrigated daily, using automatic drip irrigation system, with a basic nutrient solution (Poly-Feed Drip 20–20–20 with micronutrients). In order to provide aeration of soil and prevent waterlogging, good drainage was ensured. The fertigation rate and frequency was the same for all the treatments and adjusted to the plant phenology and to the climatic conditions in the greenhouse. Three weeks after transplanting, faba bean seedlings were treated with NaCl salinity applied in a nutrient solution as follows: NaCl₀ – control (basic nutrient solution without added NaCl), NaCl₅₀ (control + 50 mM NaCl) and NaCl₁₀₀ (control + 100 mM NaCl). Randomized block design with three replicates was applied in the experiment. Five weeks after salinity treatment started (at the pod filling stage), faba bean leaf intercellular CO₂ concentration (C_i, μmol mol⁻¹), stomatal conductance (g_s, mol H₂O m⁻² s⁻¹), transpiration rate (E, mol H₂O m⁻² s⁻¹) and photosynthetic rate (A, μmol CO₂ m⁻² s⁻¹) were measured in a triplicate, on a youngest fully developed leaf, with LCpro+ portable photosynthesis system (ADC BioScientific Ltd., Great Britain). Chlorophyll content index (CCI) was measured at the same time and on the same leaf with a CCM-200 plus Chlorophyll Content Meter (ADC BioScientific Ltd., Great Britain). Obtained data were subjected to the analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the SAS statistical software package (SAS Institute, 2007). The significance of differences between the means was determined with Tukey's HSD test at P<0.05.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Influence of raising irrigation water salinity on faba bean leaf intercellular CO₂ concentration, stomatal conductance, transpiration rate, photosynthetic rate and chlorophyll content index is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Effect of irrigation water salinity (0, 50 and 100 mM NaCl) on faba bean leaf intercellular CO₂ concentration (C_i, μmol mol⁻¹), stomatal conductance (g_s, mol H₂O m⁻² s⁻¹), transpiration rate (E, mol H₂O m⁻² s⁻¹), photosynthetic rate (A, μmol CO₂ m⁻² s⁻¹) and chlorophyll content index (CCI).

NaCl treatment	Intercellular CO ₂ concentration (C _i)	Transpiration rate (E)	Stomatal conductance (g _s)	Photosynthetic rate (A)	Chlorophyll content index
	μmol mol ⁻¹	mol H ₂ O m ⁻² s ⁻¹	mol H ₂ O m ⁻² s ⁻¹	μmol CO ₂ m ⁻² s ⁻¹	(CCI)
NaCl ₀	144 _A	2.61 _A	0.16 _A	18 _A	64.7 _{AB}
NaCl ₅₀	126.6 _A	1.71 _B	0.09 _B	12.1 _B	83.7 _A
NaCl ₁₀₀	151.4 _A	1.46 _B	0.08 _B	10.2 _B	52.9 _B
Statistical significance	n.s.	P<0.01	P<0.01	P<0.01	P=0.01

Faba bean leaf C_i was not significantly affected by application of saline irrigation water (Table 1). C_i estimations, which are estimations of the CO_2 mole fraction at the evaporating sites, are assuming that photosynthesis and transpiration are fairly uniform over the leaf area (Meyer and Genty, 1998). However, this is proved not to be as adequate when g_s decreases due to environmental impacts, as is the case in this research, because of the non-uniform distribution of the stomatal aperture and photosynthesis (Meyer and Genty, 1998). It is considered that the concentration of CO_2 in chloroplasts decreases because of lower g_s , in spite of the apparent stability of CO_2 concentration in intercellular spaces (Gama et al., 2007). Thus, decreased g_s and A do suggest faba bean lower CO_2 uptake under saline conditions, even though this could not be assumed only by observing C_i values. In this context, decreased g_s and A , as lower CO_2 uptake rate leads to lower photosynthesis rate (Mansour et al., 2008), could prove to be a better indicators of plant CO_2 uptake rate under stressful environmental conditions, such as increased soil salinity.

Stomatal conductance, transpiration and photosynthetic rate of faba bean plants irrigated with saline water significantly decreased ($P < 0.01$) in regard to control plants, but without significant difference amongst salinity treatments (Table 1). Plant salt stress actually comprises (ionic and) osmotic stress, which reduces water availability to plants (Ondrasek et al., 2006). The osmotic effect of salinity stress, which is considered to continue for the duration of exposure of plants to salinity, may result in stomatal closure (Carillo et al., 2011). Lower g_s of salt stressed bean plants suggested that raised soil salinity imposed water limitation for plants, causing them osmotic stress. As a part of an adaptive response to salt stress, plants try to retain water by stomatal closure, causing a decrease of both, transpiration and photosynthetic rate, which is in agreement with our results (Table 1). Therefore, application of saline irrigation water, due to stomatal effects of plant salt stress, results in decreased rate of transpiration and limits faba bean photosynthesis as well. This is additionally confirmed by the same trend in g_s , E as well as A in regard to salinity treatments.

Even though osmotic adaptation was found to be low or even absent in faba beans (Stoddard et al., 2006), our results could suggest otherwise. Adaptation of plants to osmotic stress is actually a plant response to maintain water relations. It usually includes osmotically active substances (Stoddard et al., 2006), which were not a part of this research. Yet, decreased g_s along with the fact that all plants in the experiment completed their life cycle despite decreased soil water potential caused by salinity, point out the possibility that the osmotic adaptation is not yet well elucidated for faba beans. Furthermore, lower stomatal density, which we suggested earlier as a possibility, is actually associated with water conserving attributes and indicates better adaptation to water stress conditions (Khan et al., 2010). However, further research, focused on the faba bean possible adaptation to water stress, is needed.

Salinity treatments significantly affected CCI ($P = 0.01$), although the difference was found to be only between the salinity treatments themselves (Table 1). It is considered that plant salt stress may cause inhibition of chlorophyll biosynthesis, increase of its degradation by chlorophyllase, as well as the oxidative stress which could lead to degradation of chloroplast structure and decrease in chlorophyll content (Azooz et al., 2013). Absence of the significant difference between CCI of control plants and CCI of NaCl treated plants (Table 1) emphasized the importance of stomatal over non-stomatal effects of salt stress on faba bean photosynthesis. Otherwise, as non-stomatal effects of salinity on plant photosynthesis include

inhibition of chlorophyll biosynthesis or increase of its degradation which would have been reflected on CCI, significant difference between CCI of control plants and salinity treated plants is expected.

CONCLUSION

Decreased g_s and A suggest faba bean lower CO_2 uptake under saline conditions, even though this could not be assumed only by observing C_i values. In this context, decreased g_s and A could prove to be a better indicators of plant CO_2 uptake rate under saline conditions. Lower g_s of salt stressed bean plants suggested that raised soil salinity imposed water limitation for plants, causing them osmotic stress. Therefore, application of saline irrigation water, due to stomatal effects of plant salt stress, results in decreased rate of transpiration and limits faba bean photosynthesis as well. Absence of the significant difference between CCI of control plants and CCI of NaCl treated plants emphasized the importance of stomatal over non-stomatal effects of salt stress on faba bean photosynthesis. Screening for the crops that could maintain photosynthetic activity in a saline environment could provide a basis for identification of salt tolerance in horticultural crops.

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